

Interfacial damage in fibre reinforced composites modelled in the framework of finite elements with embedded regions

S.V. Lomov¹, P. Druzhinin^{2,3}, Q. Liu¹, F. Lu⁴, D. Vandepitte² and L. Gorbatikh¹

¹Department of Materials Engineering, KU Leuven, Belgium

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, KU Leuven, Belgium

³SIM vzw, Technologiepark 935, B-9052 Zwijnaarde, Belgium

⁴Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics, P.R. China

Contents

1. Introduction. Embedded elements in modelling of fibre reinforced composites
2. Combination of cohesive and embedded elements
3. Validation of the method
4. Application: Interplay between multiple toughening mechanisms in nanocomposites
5. Application: Debonding of misaligned UD fibres
6. Conclusion

1. Introduction. Embedded elements in modelling of fibre reinforced composites

2. Combination of cohesive and embedded elements
3. Validation of the method
4. Application: Interplay between multiple toughening mechanisms in nanocomposites
5. Application: Debonding of misaligned UD fibres
6. Conclusion

Mesh superposition/embedded elements for fibrous composites

Publication	Term used and scope	Illustration
Fish, 1992	s-element	
Zako et al, 2005	M3 method, textiles	
Jiang et al, 2008	Domain superposition, textiles	
larve et al, 2009	Independent mesh, textiles	
Tabatabaei et al, 2014 – 2016	Embedded elements, fibres & textiles	
Romanov et al, 2013 – 2015	EE, nanotubes	
Liu et al, 2018 – 2019	EE, nanotubes, optimisation	

A gallery

1. Introduction. Embedded elements in modelling of fibre reinforced composites
- 2. Combination of cohesive and embedded elements**
3. Validation of the method
4. Application: Interplay between multiple toughening mechanisms in nanocomposites
5. Application: Debonding of misaligned UD fibres
6. Conclusions

Embedded elements – cohesive zone model (EE – CZM)

(a) Conventional direct FE model

(b) EE-CZM FE model

- add cohesive elements on the fibre surface;
- embed nodes on the outer surface of cohesive elements into host elements;
- connect nodes on inner surface of cohesive elements with fibre surface nodes.

[Liu, Q., L. Gorbatikh and S. V. Lomov (2019). Composite Structures 223: 110921]

Volume redundancy: fibre stiffness reduction

$$\sigma(x) = C_R \epsilon(x)$$

$$C_R = C_R(x) - C_M$$

The fibre stiffness reduction, with the matrix stiffness unchanged, leads to gross errors after debonding

Volume redundancy: matrix stiffness reduction

larve EV, Mollenhauer DH, Zhou EG, Breitzman T, Whitney TJ (2009)
Composites Part A 40:1880-90

Debonding development

1. Introduction. Embedded elements in modelling of fibre reinforced composites
2. Combination of cohesive and embedded elements

3. Validation of the method

4. Application: Interplay between multiple toughening mechanisms in nanocomposites
5. Application: Debonding of misaligned UD fibres
6. Conclusion

Cox' problem

strain energy, 10^{-18} J

	Fiber	Matrix	Interface
Direct	0.702	26.373	2.91×10^{-2}
EE-CZM	0.716	26.379	3.03×10^{-2}
Error (%)	2.08	2.31×10^{-2}	4.20

Wavy fibre

Straight fibre pull-out

Wavy fibre pull-out

Random fibres, transverse loading

direct FE

EE - CZM

direct FE

EE - CZM

1. Introduction. Embedded elements in modelling of fibre reinforced composites
2. Combination of cohesive and embedded elements
3. Validation of the method

4. Application: Interplay between multiple toughening mechanisms in nanocomposites

5. Application: Debonding of misaligned UD fibres
6. Conclusion

Toughness improvement?

Damage mechanisms induced by CNTs:

- Nano-scale : *pullout and bridging of CNT* ↔ CNT/matrix interface
 - Micro-scale : *crack pinning, deflection, etc.* ↔ Morphology of CNT assemblies
- } Dual-scale FE model

uniform distribution:
marginal improvement in strength and toughness

optimized distribution:
strength **doubled**, toughness (energy) **trippled**

How and why?

Micro-scale

- Delay in damage initiation
- Damage diffusion
- Crack branching

Nano-scale

- CNT debonding
- CNT pull-out

Effect of interfacial strength

Interfacial shear strength (CNT/epoxy):

- Pristine: $\tau = 30 \text{ MPa}$
- After functionalization: $\tau = 151 \text{ MPa}$

Effects on damage initiation and development

Damage contours at strain of 1.0%

Delay in damage initiation is insensitive to τ

Damage contours at maximum stress

Damage diffusion is significantly enhanced by a moderate increase of τ

1. Introduction. Embedded elements in modelling of fibre reinforced composites
2. Combination of cohesive and embedded elements
3. Validation of the method
4. Application: Interplay between multiple toughening mechanisms in nanocomposites

5. Application: Debonding of misaligned UD fibres

6. Conclusion

FE models with wavy misaligned fibres

1. Two basic models with 3 and 6 degrees of the average misalignment are generated by means of ANSYS RVE Generator (uses perturbation methods to converge to the desired misalignment).
2. Model dimensions: 30 x 30 x 65 μm .
3. Varying proximity between fibres due to randomised fibre directions.

Basic model with average misalignment angle $\vartheta = 6^\circ$

Debonding evolution (6° misalignment, weak interface)

Step: Step-1 Frame: 0
Total Time: 0.000000

$D = 1$ for complete de-bonding

De-bonded area – number of cohesive elements out of total, in which D reached 1

Parametric study

Comparison 3° vs 6°, weak interface

Red curve – $G_{n,t} = 2 \text{ J/m}^2$; blue curve – $G_{n,t} = 10 \text{ J/m}^2$; green curve – $G_{n,t} = 25 \text{ J/m}^2$; pink curve – $G_{n,t} = 50 \text{ J/m}^2$

Comparison 3° vs 6° (all interface properties)

De-bonded area, %

De-bonded area, %

Red curve – $t_{n,t} = 40$ MPa; blue curve – $t_{n,t} = 60$ MPa; green curve – $t_n = 85$ MPa, $t_t = 125$ MPa

see also:

Liu Q, Lomov SV, Gorbatiikh L
"Competition between
different toughening
mechanisms in composites
with carbon nanotube
grafted fibers", ICCM-22,
Monday 12th, 2019
Nanocomposites, 17:30

1. Introduction. Embedded elements in modelling of fibre reinforced composites
2. Combination of cohesive and embedded elements
3. Validation of the method
4. Application: Interplay between multiple toughening mechanisms in nanocomposites
5. Application: Debonding of misaligned UD fibres

6. Conclusion

Combination of embedded elements and cohesive zone:
modelling of all types of damage in fibrous materials ...
... including interface debonding ...
... with simple meshes ...
... for extremely complex fibres geometry

Acknowledgments

The work has been funded by:

- KU Leuven Research Council (C24/16/021),
- China Scholarship Council
- SIM/VLAIO (Flanders) in RELFICOM project belonging to NANOFORCE program.